

SCIENTIFIC-PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF THE ACTIVITY OF NECESSARY PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article, the main terms encountered in the scientific pedagogical activity of the future physical education teacher, the correct organization of pedagogical activity, the special attention of future physical education teachers during their scientific pedagogical activity necessary aspects and the need for an approach, as well as the organization of innovative and technological activities of the future physical education teacher are discussed.*

Key words : *Physical education, pedagogical activity, pedagogical skill, innovative activity of the future physical education teacher, creativity, technological approach.*

НАУЧНО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ НЕОБХОДИМЫХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ВОСПИТАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены основные условия, встречающиеся в научно-педагогической деятельности будущего учителя физической культуры, правильная организация педагогической деятельности, особое внимание будущих учителей физической культуры в ходе их научно-педагогической деятельности, необходимые аспекты и необходимость подхода, а также организация инновационно-технологической деятельности будущего учителя физической культуры.*

Ключевые слова: *физическое воспитание, педагогическая деятельность, педагогическое мастерство, инновационная деятельность будущего учителя физической культуры, креативность, технологический подход.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the priorities of our country's policy is to raise a generation that is both physically and mentally healthy. Because today, in the conditions of globalization processes that are intensifying in the countries of the world, raising a highly moral and physically fit generation is one of the most important factors that determine the future of our country and realize the noble goals of our people. In the implementation of this good deed, its legal foundations have been created, and extensive work is being done. In particular, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev of June 3, 2017 "On measures for the development of physical education and mass sports" No. Decree No. PF-5368 "On measures to fundamentally improve the management system" is of particular importance in the further development of this field. One of the main goals of these decrees and decisions is to deepen the theoretical and practical knowledge in this field, to correctly formulate the concepts and terms of skills and qualifications related to physical education. In fact, at a time when the processes of globalization are becoming more and more intense, the attention paid to physical education teachers, who are directly involved in the general and special physical training of young people, is gaining importance in this regard. After all, one of their important services is to direct students to educational, cultural, medical, industrial construction, and production professions, and secondly, they serve to a certain extent to arm them with special physical training. Today, the teachers teaching the young generation must fully master modern innovative technologies, have the skills

to use information and communication tools wisely, and be familiar with all the secrets of education. will be done.

When studying the issues related to the scientific pedagogical activity of physical education teachers, first of all, it is appropriate to analyze the content and essence of the concepts related to this phenomenon. In particular, we can see that the concept of "physical education" itself has been given several definitions. "Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at improving the human body morphologically and functionally, forming and improving basic movement skills, skills, and related knowledge important for his life " [3]. Definitions such as "Physical education aimed at all-round training of the body, education aimed at strengthening health , physical exercises" are given [13].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In different directions, whether he is a mathematician, physicist, historian or physical education teacher, his work style is directly related to pedagogical activity . The meaningful and high-quality conduct of the lesson , in turn, is closely related to his pedagogical skills, pedagogical skills, pedagogical competence, and pedagogical activity in general. The famous Russian pedagogue V. A. Sukhomlinsky : "One of the secrets of pedagogical leadership is to arouse interest in teachers' regular research and analysis of their work. " Whoever tries to distinguish between good and bad in his lessons, in his interactions with students, and to share his achievements and shortcomings in time, will have achieved half the success of pedagogical activity" expressed [12]. From this point of view, a young future physical education teacher, who has just started his pedagogical activity, cannot relax physically and mentally or completely relax.

As we know, this feeling is called "relaxation" in psychology, and it is recognized as an assessment of negative situations in people's work. In order for each physical education teacher to fully master the pedagogical skills: first, he must have mastered the educational subject based on the requirements of the time; secondly, to have psychological and pedagogical knowledge (to be able to use methods appropriate to the character of students); thirdly, it is important that it contains pedagogical curiosity and self-sacrifice. Russian scientist I. P. Rachenko expresses the following opinion about pedagogical skills as a part of pedagogical art: "Pedagogical skills are the teacher's perfect mastery of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, professional qualifications and skills, interest in his profession, developed pedagogical thinking. and intuition, moral-aesthetic attitude to life, confidence in one's own reasoning and firm will are understood" [11].

Also, in the pedagogical activities of the future physical education teacher, it is most important for the future physical education teacher to be devoted to the teaching profession, to have a perfect knowledge of the teaching methodology of his subject, to be able to demonstrate his pedagogical skills, and to be able to use pedagogical techniques properly. is one of the important components.

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that every future physical education teacher is always engaged in education and upbringing of students and interacts with them in parallel with delivering physical exercises to students. Since every student is constantly developing mentally, spiritually and physically, the future teacher should be in constant communication with them, taking into account each of their psychological character and physiological characteristics, the mechanisms

of influence. , first of all, it is necessary to study the theory of psychology and education in a perfect way, and constantly develop his professional activity. In this regard, we believe that future physical education teachers should pay special attention to the following during their scientific pedagogical activities:

mastery of the system of knowledge on physical education ;

having the skills and qualifications to fully deliver physical exercises to students; - knowledge of the basis of general methodological sciences, in particular, current issues of state policy, together with the mastery of one's own science;

- to be able to independently analyze the social problems and processes taking place around them from their point of view ;

- acquiring knowledge about the spiritual image of students during the educational process

- able to apply modern pedagogical and psychological knowledge based on the age characteristics of the students ;

- able to independently acquire new knowledge , improve it and use it on a scientific basis in one's work;

- being able to use regulatory legal documents individually in their scientific and pedagogical activities;

- compliance with the culture of the problem;

- able to analyze acquired knowledge based on a critical approach;

- able to clearly convey the acquired knowledge to the students ;

- the formation of a sense of responsibility for one's profession;

mastered one of the foreign languages as a means of professional qualification or scientific communication exchange during the pedagogical activity ;

- ability to effectively use modern information technologies;

- ability to use modern pedagogical technologies in pedagogical activities , etc. Also, future physical education teachers must have a perfect knowledge of the terms of physical culture used in their pedagogical activities. Of course, the use of terms by the teacher in a comprehensible, clear and appropriate manner has a direct impact on the quality of the student's physical training.

In fact, we all use the terms of physical culture today in our daily life. We can meet them and come across them in almost all subjects in educational institutions . It should be noted that "today there are more than 15,000 concepts and terms specific to about 300 sports that exist worldwide " [10]. Physical education teachers should be able to speak deeply, impressively, logically, beautifully in the process of working with students in their pedagogic activities, and should be able to use expressions of educational importance. must be able to use it. It should not be forgotten that the speech of the teacher is a source of example for every student, even if he carelessly provokes his anger and violates discipline, not by rude treatment, insults, humiliation, touching his personality, but should have the ability to get out of the situation with a positive approach. While the teacher conducts the lesson, his voice should be a tool to control the audience. During the explanation of exercises related to physical education, he should be able to express what the students should emphasize by raising and lowering his voice at the appropriate place.

DISCUSSION

It is possible to consider the following specific approaches that play an important role in the scientific and pedagogical activities of future physical education teachers: 1. Creative

approach . 2. Innovative approach. 3. Technological approach. Every future physical education teacher should be able to find ways to interest his students in the lesson based on a creative approach during the lesson . In this regard, the famous psychologist Dale Carnegie said, "There is only one way to motivate and interest a person to do something. And if it is, it is to awaken a real desire to do the work in that person's heart. Coercion and torture do not work..." [4], it is not for nothing that he emphasized, of course. At this point, it is appropriate to comment on the concept of creativity. "Creativity" (from the English "create" - to create, "creative" [6] - the ability of a future teacher to quickly make decisions related to the solution of problems encountered in the course of classes and their solution represents a high-level new creative approach. In the dictionary of pedagogical terms , creativity is explained as follows: "Creativity (creativity) is a mental process that leads to the ability to create something new, unique, thinking, idea and solution" [8].

Creativity is the readiness of the future teacher to create new ideas and positively solve existing problems aimed at ensuring the effectiveness of training, unlike the traditional approach and thinking of students in the process of training, clearly the ability to find a solution to the existing problems and eliminate them in order to achieve the goal is formed, it helps to solve the problems that have arisen by chance in a reasonable and quick manner. It can be seen that creativity is manifested in the scientific pedagogical activity of future physical education teachers in the following cases: - the fluency of the teacher's thought and speech; - the teacher can direct his thoughts according to a clearly defined goal; - uniqueness (originality) in the teacher's creativity; - the curiosity of the teacher, the creativity of new ideas, the breadth of imagination, the ability to create hypotheses; - study of the student's ability, ability and accurate assessment; - the teacher has mastered the science methodology and applied it to the educational process; - the teacher creatively shares ideas with his colleagues on new information about science achievements; - able to independently learn advanced foreign experiences related to the teacher's field and apply them in practice; - the teacher continuously improves his knowledge, skills and qualifications; - the teacher can gain the student's trust, find a way to his heart and communicate with him. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "Today we are moving to the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and community life. It's not for nothing, of course.

Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? A country that relies on new ideas, new ideas, and innovation will win . " Innovation is the future" [1] is also important. After all, it is difficult to imagine today's education sector without innovation. On the other hand, based on the nature of the era, the need to create new pedagogical technologies in preparing future physical education teachers for innovative activities, and managing the activities of students in the educational process is, first of all, a direct effect of physical education training. It should not be forgotten that it is inextricably linked with the education of a well-rounded person. The main features of the innovative activity of physical education teachers are expressed in the following:

- 1) harmonizing the philosophy of creative activity with concepts of physical education ;
- 2) acquisition of pedagogical research methods;
- 3) ability to create author's concepts;
- 4) ability to plan and carry out experimental work;
- 5) to be able to use the experiences of other researchers-pedagogues;
- 6) cooperation with colleagues;

to exchange ideas and provide methodical assistance ;

8) prevention and elimination of conflicts;

9) applying innovations to physical education lessons, being able to adapt them to one's own conditions [2]. Therefore, the innovative activity in the scientific pedagogical activity of the future physical education teacher is manifested in the following: - creative approach; - creative activity; - technological and methodological training in delivering news; - new thinking; - based on national and universal values in the culture of behavior; - application of new pedagogical technologies; - in professional skills. Based on the above, it is no exaggeration to say that innovative activity is one of the main factors that determine all the successes of a physical education teacher, a process that increases his professional and pedagogical skills and positively affects the quality of education . . In the course of today's global changes , the need for an innovative approach in the continuing education system is increasing. In particular, it creates the need for an innovative approach to physical education based on modern pedagogical technologies. The innovative approach can be considered as a process of continuously organizing the educational process based on innovations with new ideas , technologies, modern interactive methods, and is formed and improved during the teacher's research. The implementation of an innovative approach by a future physical education teacher in the educational process brings the essence of his pedagogical activity to a new perspective. The technological approach is of great importance in the effectiveness of the scientific pedagogical activity of the future physical education teacher . We believe that technologies should be distinguished from certain techniques or methods of influence.

In particular, the dictionaries explain that "technique (Greek *techne* - art, skill, ability) is a set of skills and methods used in a certain activity" [7]. In some scientific sources, it is defined as "technique (*techne*-skill, art) - a set of means and methods of changing and mastering nature in order to satisfy the material needs of man " [5]. In the national encyclopedia, a more precise definition of technology is used , that is, "technology is a set of tools and skills that allow a person to influence the surrounding nature in order to obtain material wealth and meet the needs of people and society. Its main task is to ease human labor and increase labor productivity. It allows effective use of natural resources , mastering the depths of the earth, the world's oceans, and outer space ” [14], it was explained. So, we can say that technology is a set of methods and guidelines that can be used in any field , and it is the main tool of the human activity process. "Technology - 1) a pedagogical phenomenon that embodies the laws of personal training , upbringing and development and guarantees the final result; 2) education is also defined as a classification of methods of organization of the educational process, its management, organization of pedagogical and educational activities" [9]. Therefore, a part of the technological approach is a set of specific methods of pedagogical activity that show ways to eliminate problems that arise on the way to a specific goal set by teachers to improve the quality of education. is considered The technological approach consists of certain necessary elements: - goals and tasks; - primary sources; - strategic and tactical programs of resource use; - methodology of using resources; - principles of conducting certain events; - development of projects; - such as making work plans. We believe that it is appropriate for a future physical education teacher to carry out scientific pedagogical activities based on the following technological process: - gathering new knowledge; - bringing into one system; - step-by-step delivery of accumulated knowledge to students. Therefore, the technological approach creates

new opportunities for the teacher to comprehensively analyze various innovative trends, as well as solve problems that may arise during the course of the lesson.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above analysis, it is possible to draw the following conclusion: firstly, the ongoing comprehensive reforms are not only the issue of personnel training in various fields, but also the need to fundamentally improve the scientific and pedagogical activities of personnel in the field of physical education in educational institutions; secondly, the analysis of the issues related to the scientific pedagogical activity of the future physical education teachers shows that, despite the existence of views and sources on the topic, it shows the need to research this issue purely pedagogically; thirdly, it is desirable for the future physical education teacher to create the necessary conditions for the thorough assimilation of knowledge, taking into account the interests, abilities and requirements of the students, using the modern achievements of the science and pedagogical technologies in the course of their scientific-pedagogical activity; fourthly, today's future physical education teachers need to be able to effectively use creative, innovative, and technological approaches that play an important role in their scientific and pedagogical activities; fifthly, every teacher should aim to develop pure-minded, brave, well-behaved, determined, morally and physically mature individuals in the course of classes. This, in turn, will be the basis for the formation of mature personnel who will serve the development of our country in the future.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shakhkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. - T. "Uzbekistan" NMIU, 2018. - P.19-20.
2. Abdullaeva Sh.A., Khurramov E.E. Preparation of future physical education teachers for innovative activities // Modern education / Sovremennoe obrazovanie. 2016. No. 5. – B.15-16.
3. Abdullaev A., Honkeldiev Sh. Theory and methodology of physical education. Study guide. T., UzDJTI, 2005. p. 12.
4. Carnegie D. Confession is not defeat. Art magazine. T.: 2009. p. 28.
5. Mamashokirov S. Panic or truth. "ECONOMY - FINANCE", 2012, -192 - p.
6. Muslimov. N.A., Usmonboeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., Toraev A.B. Fundamentals of pedagogical competence and creativity / - Tashkent, 2015.
7. Ojegov S.I. Slovar Russian language. - Moscow: "Russky yazyk", 1984. - S. 692.
8. Dictionary of pedagogical terms. Author group. "Fan" publishing house of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T.: 2008. - B.64.
9. Dictionary of pedagogical terms. Author group. "Fan" publishing house of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T.: 2008. - B.130.
10. Rafiev H.T. Some problems of concepts and terms in the field of physical culture // Proceedings of the international scientific conference on the topic of modern trends in the development of theory and methodology of physical education and sports . - Chirchiq, 2019. - B. 49.